

A Study on Gender Equality in Sustainable Development Goals(SDGs) with Special Reference to Chhattisgarh State, India

¹Aarti Rathour, ²Dr. Rajbhanu Patel
¹Research Scholar, ²Assistant professor,
 Department of Economics,
 Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya Bilaspur,
 Chhattisgarh, India. Email:

³Keshav Singh Rathour
³Research Scholar,
 Department of Tourism Management,
 Indira Gandhi National Tribal University,
 Amarkantak, Madhya Pradesh, India

Abstract:-Today, all the countries of the world are competing to overtake each other on the path of development. Every possible measure is being taken, from industrialization to exploitation of natural resources. In this race for Development, we have forgotten at what worth we want to achieve it. With particular emphasis on SDG 2030, the purpose of this study is to evaluate Chhattisgarh's progress on gender equality. This study has attempted to measure the actual progress of gender equality of Chhattisgarh. It is descriptive in nature. SDGs India Index scores constructed by NITI Aayog in 2021. It is used for analysis according to the NITI Aayog's SDG India Index report 2020–21, Chhattisgarh has been named the best-performing state in India for the Sustainable Development Goals' gender equality criterion. The index, which was created in India in partnership with the UN, gauges advancement at the national and subnational levels. This paper attempts to understand the challenges encountered by Chhattisgarh in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. The paper also attempts to suggest measures to overcome the challenges.

Keywords:- SDGs, Gender equality, Performance of Chhattisgarh, Challenges.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the 70th meeting of the United Nations General Assembly in 2015, under the 'Agenda for Sustainable Development 2030, 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their 169 objectives were adopted by the member states. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and "2030 Agenda" sound for all-round feat to ensure better health, gender equality, poverty alleviation, and peace and prosperous living for all. Of which Goal 3 focuses solely on health, ensuring "the promotion of healthy living and wellness for all age groups." SDG 3 consists of 13 goals, with four listed as "means of implementation" goals. Other selected targets highlight health goals, including eliminating malnutrition of all forms, universal and equitable access to hygienic conditions, clean water to drink, and health care.

Sustainable Development Goals is defined as "development that meets the needs of present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Lee, S. W., & Xue, K., 2021). Being equally fair to men and women is the goal of gender equity. Strategies

and procedures that make up for women's historical and societal flaws, which hinder women and men from otherwise competing on an even playing field, must frequently be made available in order to ensure impartiality. Equality results from equity. The equal enjoying of socially valuable goods, opportunities, resources, and rewards by men and women is a requirement for gender equality. In situations where there is gender disparity, women are typically left out or treated unfairly when it comes to making decisions and having access to financial and social resources. Ending all discrimination against women and girls is a basic human right and is a prerequisite for sustainable development. Goal 5 calls for ending all forms of violence, trafficking and sexual exploitation of women and girls. Recognizing and valuing unpaid care and domestic work is a key component of this goal, with a focus on the significance of women's leadership opportunities at all levels of decision-making in political, economic, and public life, as well as their full and effective involvement in those opportunities. As per United Nation Report, at the current time, 1 in 5 women and girls between the ages of 15-49 have reported experiencing physical or sexual violence by an intimate partner and as many as 49 countries of the world currently have no laws protecting women from domestic violence (UNDP 2019).

Through a robust legal system, negative practices that target women must be eradicated. To achieve greater gender equality, it is necessary to give women equal rights to land, property, sexual and reproductive wellness, technology, and social media, and at the same time to facilitate and encourage more political participation and leadership by women (UNICEF 2019). Most countries of the world which aim for a sustainable future are striving hard to achieve the goal of gender equality and to end all sorts of discrimination against women and girls (Dhingra & Bala, 2020).

The fact is quite disturbing that in India women and girls are not only experiencing inequalities in access to health care, education, nutrition, utilization and asset ownership, but also are living in an environment full of violence and discrimination (Dhingra & Bala, 2020). Though following the sustainable development goals (SDGs) laid by the United Nations India is also trying to empower women to live dignified lives, contributing as equal collaborators in the maturation and development of the nation (Dhingra & Bala, 2020). India's commitment towards undertaking reforms to

guarantee gender equality is reflected in a number of statute laws which are ordained to ensure equal opportunities and self-worth for women (Boraian, M. P., 2008). Many states level and national-level programs and policies have been established to attain the target laid by UNDP (SDG India Index, 2021).

II. OBJECTIVE

- To analyze the gender equality performance of Chhattisgarh with special reference to SDGs 2030.
- To study initiatives by government for reducing gender equality.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This conducted study is analytical and descriptive in nature. It uses secondary sources of data. United Nation has clearly set down SDGs and each SDG has several targets and indicators. In this research SDGs-5 metrics based on availability of data for the Chhattisgarh and India is done. The data has been taken from SDGs INDIA INDEX & DASHBOARD 2020-21 has been collected compiled by Niti Aayog in 2018. In support to this Census Report 2011, NFHS-4 Labor Bureau Report and National Indicator Framework (NIF) by Ministry of Statistics and Program Implementation (MOSPI) are referred. The study is split into four portions for easier comprehension. Section One deals with the methodology adopted for the construction of SDG Indian Index with respect to SDG 5. Section two gives insightful information on the SDGs performance at national level. Section three presents State-wise performance in SDG

5. Last section throws light on the indicator wise performance.

IV. PERFORMANCE OF CHHATTISGARH IN GENDER EQUALITY SDG-5

As SDG 5 is concerned, based on the data availability and to ensure performance of Chhattisgarh, Niti Aayog identified six priority indicators keeping the National Indicator Framework as base. The indicators capture four out of nine targets of SDG5. Figure-2 provide the details of global targets and national level indicators outlined under SDG5: Gender Equality (Niti Aayog, 2018; NIF, 2016).

A. First Indicator- Sex Ratio:

The sex composition, which is established by the sex ratio at birth, is one of the most important demographic and social indices for determining the status of men and women in society. In India, the sex ratio is calculated regarding the number of females per thousand males (Dey, 2015). It is a detailed indicator of the fundamental realities of Indian society. Due to a number of variables, including early marriage, the age of the mother at childbirth, sex-selective abortion, infanticide, infant and maternal mortality, health risks for women, migration, and a strong preference for having male children, India has a highly skewed gender ratio. The goal of the sex ratio is set at 950 in the explanatory note of the SDG index in India. But at present, the sex ratio at birth is 899 females per 1000 males. It has also found that only two States, namely Chhattisgarh and Kerala are above the target with a sex ratio at birth of 963 and 959 respectively (SDG India Index and Dashboard 2021-22).

Year	India		Chhattisgarh	
	sex ratio	Child sex ratio	sex ratio	Child sex ratio
2001	933	927	991	975
2011	943	919	989	969

Table 1: Performance of the Sex Ratio (Female per 1000 Male) in Chhattisgarh,

Source: Census of India

State/UT	Sex Ratio at Birth (female per 1000 Male)	Index Score
Chhattisgarh	958	64
Madhya Pradesh	925	55
Jharkhand	923	51
Odisha	933	46

Table 2: Performance of the Birth Sex Ratio (Female per 1000 Male) in Chhattisgarh and their neighboring state.

Source: Index & Dashboard 2020-21

Concerning Chhattisgarh and the state that is adjacent to it Table 2 demonstrates that Chhattisgarh, with a sex ratio at birth of 958, did well in achieving this goal. However, in the case of Jharkhand, it is only 923.

B. Second Indicator- Salary Parity:

The equality of average incomes and wages between men and women is another measure of gender parity. Although equal pay for men and women is the country's stated goal, women in India only receive 70% of the salary for comparable work as their men equivalents.

State/UT	Ratio of female to male average wage/salary earnings received Among regular wage/salaried employees
Chhattisgarh	0.64
Madhya Pradesh	0.75
Jharkhand	0.58
Odisha	0.65
India	0.74

Table 3: Ratio of female to male average wage/salary earnings received Among regular wage/salaried employees

Source: Index & Dashboard 2020-21

Table 3 reflects that chhattisgarh, madhyapradesh, and odisha are performing well in this indicator and Jharkhand low as 0.58. and in india top performer is u.p and mijoram 0.96 and 0.91 percent.

C. Third Indicator- Domestic Violence:

To fully accomplish gender equality, the proportion of women who have ever been married and have ever experienced marital abuse must be eliminated. India's index

score for this indication is 33.3, which means that one in every three ever-married adult females between the ages of 15 and 49 experiences marital violence in the form of physical, sexual, or emotional abuse. (SDG India Index, 2018) Overall Crime Rate against women was lower than the national average in 2015 (44.8 as compared to 53.9) and the existence of social crimes such as dowry deaths, cruelty by husbands and relatives lower than neighboring states.

State/UT	Rate of crimes against women per 1,00,000 female population	Per lakh women who have experienced cruelty/physical violence By husband or his relatives during the year
Chhattisgarh	53.5	5.09
Madhya Pradesh	69.0	14.57
Jharkhand	47.8	6.40
Odisha	103.5	12.79
India	62.4	19.54

Table 4: Percentage of women aged 15 to 49 who have ever been married and had experienced domestic violence

Source: Index & Dashboard 2020-21

Fig. : Crime Rate Against Women

Source: NSS

D. Fourth Indicator- Women Leadership:

Another metric that shows the level of gender parity is the percentage of seats gained by women in state legislative assembly general elections. This indicator is essential as it is generally believed that the full and equitable participation of women in public life is critical for building and sustaining strong and vibrant democracies (Pepera, 2018). However,

rhetoric does not match reality, as women have only 8.7 percent of seats in State Legislative Assemblies, despite the national goal of 50 percent of seats being held by men and women respectively. In India, no state or union territory has yet reached this goal. Among all of the country's legislative assemblies,

State/UT	Percentage of elected women over total seats in the state legislative assembly
Chhattisgarh	14.44
Madhya Pradesh	9.13
Jharkhand	12.35
Odisha	8.90
India	8.46

Table 5: Comparing the Number of Seats Won by Women in State Legislative and General Elections
Source: Index & Dashboard 2020-21

The representation of women of Chhattisgarh in the PRIs of the state is higher than the national average. It is also relatively high in Urban Local Bodies but is lower at the Vidhan and Lok Sabha levels.

E. Fifth Indicator- Female Participation in Work Force:

Gender equality is demonstrated through women's equal involvement in the workforce. In addition to boosting economic development and household income, women's labour force involvement can assist compensate for the

decreased labour force participation of males in their prime. Unfortunately, the labour force participation rate of women in India is only 33 percent than the labour force participation rate of men though the national target for 2030 is to have equal labour force participation rate for both women and men (SDG India Index, 2020). It brings out that in India, no State has achieved this mark yet SDG India Index, 2020.

State/UT	female to male Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) (15-59 years)
Chhattisgarh	0.64
Madhya Pradesh	0.36
Jharkhand	0.28
Odisha	0.32
India	0.33

Table 6: female to male Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR)

Source: Index & Dashboard 2020-21

Table 6 shows the class of aspirants with low rates of female labor force participation in all the neighboring states—Jharkhand(0.28), Odisha(0.32), Madhya Pradesh (0.36). This would suggest that the majority of Indian women take care of the home and the child. While female labour and workforce participation (FLFPR and WFPR) continue to be higher than the national average and those of neighboring states.

F. Sixth Indicator – Adoption of Family Planning Methods:

Adopting tools and strategies that enable people to choose whether and when to have children is known as family planning. An essential measure of gender equality is the proportion of women in the 15–49 age range who use contemporary family planning methods. This indicator is important because it highlights the significance of choice making by the women. (Garg and Singh 2014; Lomborg 2015). Findings reveal that in India, almost half of presently married women between the ages of 15 and 49 are using modern methods of family planning. Female sterilization is the most popular contraceptive method among women (SDG India Index, 2018).

State/UT	Percentage of currently married women aged 15-49 years who have their demand for family planning satisfied by modern methods
Chhattisgarh	79.3
Madhya Pradesh	78
Jharkhand	63.8
Odisha	64.1
India	72

Table 7: Comparison of Percentage of Women (Age 15-49) who are using Modern Methods of Family Planning

Source: Index & Dashboard 2020-21

SDG 5. GENDER EQUALITY		Chhattisgarh	India	Targets
5.1	Sex ratio at birth	958	899	950
5.2	Ratio of female to male average wage/salary earnings received among regular wage/ salaried employees	0.64	.74	1
5.3	Rate of crimes against women per 1,00,000 female population	53.5	62.4	0
5.4	Per lakh women who have experienced cruelty/physical violence by husband or his relatives during the year	5.09	19.54	0
5.5	Percentage of elected women over total seats in the state legislative assembly	14.44	8.46	50
5.6	Ratio of female to male Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) (15-59 years)	0.64	0.33	1
5.7	Proportion of women in managerial positions including women in board of directors, in listed companies (per 1,000 persons)	250	190	145
5.8	Percentage of currently married women ages 15 to 49 years who have their family planning demand to satisfied by recent methods	79.3	72	100
5.9	Operational land holding gender wise (percentage of female operated operational holdings)	13.79	13.96	50
5.10	SDG 5 Index Score	64	48	100

Table 8: Overall performance of Chhattisgarh in national level

Source: SDG India Index & Dashboard 2020-21, NITI Aayog

G. Some Initiatives by Government for reducing Gender equality

The Chhattisgarh government claims that the state has enacted policies that advocate for gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls, and as a result, numerous significant programs are being implemented. Because of this, Chhattisgarh is one of the top states in the nation for sex ratio. The goal of the Chhattisgarh government is to eradicate all sorts of discrimination and violence against women and girls. There are efforts being made to ensure women in the state equal opportunities and involvement in social, economic, and political decisions and leadership. Which programmes run by the state government include Sakhi-One Stop Center, Beti Bachao-Beti Padhao, Noni Suraksha Yojana, Nava Bihan Yojana, Saksham Yojana, and Swavalamban. The employment of information and communication technology is also encouraged in order to empower women. According to state legislation governing land, property, and other matters, women's ownership and authority are still guaranteed.

The State is aware of the safety of women and children, the Gender Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention of Prevention and Redressal) Act 2013, Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act and Chhattisgarh Prevention of Torture Act-2005 are in force. The efforts being made by the state government towards empowering women by participating in all fields in Chhattisgarh have contributed significantly. Whether it is participation with 50 percent share in panchayats or as Anganwadi workers, helpers, supervisors, suposhanmitras, mitanins, teachers or self-help groups, Women are contributing significantly role to securing the state's foundation. The service of women helpline-181 is operated in the state for emergency assistance to women and girls. Sakhi Centers is operating in 27 districts of the state to help the aggrieved women where all necessary facilities are being provided at one place. (state planning commission SDG 2030 VISSION , 2019)

V. SUGGESTIONS

To promote sustained awareness building strategies and appropriate legislative and policy action towards transformation of societal norms and values that discriminate against girls and women and perpetuate harmful gendered stereotypes and practices such as child marriage, sex discrimination in abortion, and family abuse and Tonhi (witch –hunting). To promote stakeholder and community-based participation and consultation of women in designing, review, implementation and strengthening of existing and planned policy frameworks targeted at and involving women and children. Involvement of community radio, mass media and internet for information dissemination. Awareness program with the help of NGOs/ MNGOs etc like melas, public meetings, Jan Samvads and Jan Sunwais (public dialogues and public hearings). To focus on groups with special vulnerabilities and needs such as disabled women, elderly women and women in conflict areas through appropriate policy and institutional support. To promote gender sensitization through awareness campaigns, training programs and capacity building within the institutional policy making bodies and functionaries of the state across different departments and levels including the state, district and village level To promote the collection and analysis of gender disaggregated statistics for a wide range of indicators mapping the demographic, social, political and economic status of women to guide policy and decision making processes.

VI. CONCLUSION

Chhattisgarh has won by leaving behind all the states in gender equality, one of the 16 goals. In fact, Niti Aayog's SDG India index measures and ranks the performance of states based on their progress in the field of social, economic and environment. Many important schemes are being run for the empowerment of women and girls in Chhattisgarh. Because of this, Chhattisgarh is among the top states in the country for sex ratio. The Chhattisgarh government has established a target, to eliminate all kinds of discrimination and violence against women and girls. In the state, efforts are being undertaken to give women equal opportunity and access to social, economic, and political leadership. According to the study's findings, Chhattisgarh's ranking rose as a result of improved equal pay for men and women over the past year, which has helped the state break records. Lower levels of domestic violence and criminality against women, among other things.

REFERENCES

- [1.] (2019). *state planning commission SDG 2030 VISION*. UNITED Nation.
- [2.] (2021). *SDG India index and dashboard 2020-21*. sansad marg, New Delhi: NITI Ayog.
- [3.] Boraian, M. P. (2008). *Empowerment of rural women: The deterrents & determinants*. Concept Publishing Company.
- [4.] C V, D. A. (2021). Sustainable development goal and gender equality in India. *RESEARCH GATE*
- [5.] Census (2011), *Primary Census Abstracts*, Registrar General of India, Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India, Available at: <http://www.censusindia.gov>
- [6.] Dey, Jayashree (2015), Declining Sex Ratio in Sikkim: A Spatial Analysis, *The Nehru Journal*, Vol XIII, No. 2, pp-63-73.
- [7.] Dhingra, N., & Bala, R. (2020). A Study of Gender Equality in North West Region of India with Special Reference to Sustainable Development Goals 2030. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 25, 14. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2501081420>
- [8.] Lee, S. W., & Xue, K. (2021). An integrated importance-performance analysis and modified analytic hierarchy process approach to sustainable city assessment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(44), 63346-63358.
- [9.] Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2016. *National Indicator Framework*. Retrieved from MOSPI website
- [10.] Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India, retrieved from Measures taken by the Government for gender equality/socio-economic development/empowerment of women.
- [11.] *National Family Health survey 2020-21*. ministry of health and family welfare .
- [12.] Neerja, D., & rajni bala. (2020). A study of Gender equality in North region of in India with special reference to sustainable development goal 2030 .
- [13.] Niti Aayog. (2021). *SDG India Index-Baseline Report*. Retrieved from www.niti.gov.in
- [14.] Pepera, Sandra (2018), Why Women in Politics?, <https://womendeliver.org/2018/why-women-inpolitics>
- [15.] Pepera, Sandra (2018), Why Women in Politics?, <https://womendeliver.org/2018/why-women-inpolitics/> (retrieved on 22/08/2022).
- [16.] Sustainable Development Goals (2022, Sep 20). retrieved from <https://niti.gov.in/verticals/sustainable-dev-goals>